

**MODERN CROP PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES
(AS AN EXAMPLE OF INDIA)****Shermatov Khalil Khusanovich**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7197102>

Changing in the crop production practices as faster as changing of the climate within decade are not performed while other hand facing population explosion with no further increment of area under the cultivation are alarming. Climate change may define as change in the long-term alteration of temperature and typical weather patterns in a place or a particular location or the planet as a whole which cause less predictable patterns of weather. These unexpected weather patterns can make it difficult to maintain and grow crops in regions that rely on farming because expected temperature and rainfall levels can no longer be relied on. Climate change has also been connected with other damaging weather events such as more frequent and more intense hurricanes, floods, downpours, and winter storms. In some context it play wider role due to Agriculture sector accounts for 18% of the economy's output and 47% of its workforce. India is one of the larger producer of major cereals, fruits and vegetables in the world. Yet according to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, some 194 million Indians are undernourished, the largest number of hungry people in any single country. An estimated 15.2% of the population is too malnourished with third of the world's malnourished children live.

In 2015, the UN 2030 sustainable development agenda and international community committed itself to ending hunger (Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development) but roughly 800 million people worldwide suffer from hunger. And under a business as usual scenario, 8 percent of the world's population (or 650 million) will still be undernourished by

2030. Although demand is continuously growing, by 2050 we will need to produce 70 percent more food. Meanwhile, agriculture's share of global GDP has shrunk to just 3 percent, one-third its contribution just decades ago. (Clercq et al., 2018)

In conservation agriculture, achieving sustainable and profitable farming using three core principles namely minimal soil disturbance, permanent soil cover and crop rotations. There has been mass adoption of conservation agriculture around the world and it has been particularly more successful in conserve moisture, maintain or improve organic matter and reduce soil erosion.

Agriculture accounts for 30% of greenhouse gas emissions and 70% of freshwater withdrawals so attention has to be paid to energy and water use in farming. India was dependent on external food supplies in the early 1960s but introduction of HYVs for meet the growing demand of food, fiber and fuel. These HYVs were highly responsive to fertilizers and exhaustive in nature. Green revolution has greatly increased the food crop production in India without considering natural balancing; resulting most of the soils are showing sign of fatigue for sustaining higher crop production to meet the increasing food demand of the country, deterioration of water quality and highly pest infested. In current scenario there are climate change with the traditional way of crop production are going to alarming situation for food security of population explosion. So there using of modern technology of crop production with change of thinking from traditional to climate smart agriculture which are as follow:

1. Modern Technology for Crop Establishments: Field preparations are mainly concern with seedbed preparation to better crop establishments or crop standing. Seedbed are the foundation of crop establishment which are playing the key role for maintaining the initial plant population which are suppress the pest (weeds) emergence initially, later on resulted at good plant standing in field and higher yield. Hence there are field preparation should be concern economical with sustainable way.

Rice is most important cereal crop in Indian context and their production practices having puddling for water stagnation in filed but with time passes it becoming uneconomical and problematic to climate (methane emission, volatilization of nitrogen and wastage of water). In traditional practices there are repetitive tillage for field preparation and also large number of practices for leveling of field.

Laser Land leveler: Laser land leveler is one of the most effective tools for precision leveling and smoothening the agricultural land surface. Laser leveling is to use a laser guidance system to raise and lower the blade of the grading implement automatically. Laser land leveling equipment has marked one of the most significant advances in surface irrigation technology. It does not only minimize the cost of leveling but also ensures the desired degree of precision. It helps in improving resource use efficiency under surface irrigation systems by uniform distribution of irrigated water as well as resource conservation without adverse effect of environment. It minimize in time and water required to irrigate the field, more uniform distribution of water in the field, consistent

moisture environment for crops, more uniform germination and growth of crops, fertilizer, chemicals. It increases yield improves uniformity of crop maturity and reduces weeds, enhance water use efficiency and the amount of water needed for land preparation. Laser land leveling when applied under various crops and cropping patterns has resulted in water savings up to 15-30 %. Limitation behind the adoption of laser leveling is high cost and need for a skilled operator to operate. It may be less efficient in irregular and small sized fields

Bed Planting: In bed planting systems, crops are planted on the raised beds in ridge furrow system. This system is often considered more appropriate for growing high value crops that are more sensitive to temporary water logging stress. Farmers often raise crops such as cabbage, carrot, radish, okra, onion, brinjal, cauliflower, colocasia, turmeric, cotton, maize and wheat on the raised beds. Results

show that system of raised bed planting of crops may be particularly advantageous in areas where groundwater levels are falling. This tillage and crop establishment option also facilitates crop diversification and intercropping of several vegetables. The experimental results indicated that FIRB technique is not only save the resources like water and nutrients and labour but also facilitates the greater diversification of the rice-wheat cropping systems and improve the physical properties of soil.

Turbo Happy Seeder: Happy Seeder is one of the promising technologies for sowing wheat without any burning of rice residue. This technology is eco-friendly and improves the soil health as well as saves water as save the burning of residue and covering of soil help infiltration of water and prevent from evaporation. There are helps to reducing the CO₂ emission and prevent from pollute to environment.

For Sowing and Seed: There should be given equal concern to sowing of crop as such as field preparation because well prepared field are useless if there are poor crop standing in the finally which is directly related to sowing method. Huge inputs are wasted and ill impact on environment in traditional sowing practices which challenges to sustainability of crop production. Traditional practices of sowing such as broadcasting, mixed cropping etc. are several disadvantages like over seeding creates inter competition in crop or less seeding of facilitates to chances of more weeds which reduce the crop yield or failure of crop. On the other hand there seed replacement rate in Indian context is very poor which facilitate to commencement of seed borne disease and also less germination due to damaged seed or losses of viability. By changing of climate

there are concerning with changing in sowing practices and also in seeds which have mitigation ability.

Bud Cheep Cutter: Sugarcane is valuable crop especially in a country like India where over 45 million people are practicing it and a majority of them are small scale farmers. There is need of such machine which saves the sets of sugarcane used in planting. In conventional method of sugarcane cultivation, the sugarcane is cut into pieces and is buried. However, only the bud alone is required enough for cultivating sugarcane. Machine design facilitates the cutting of bud alone from the sugarcane and saves time compared to that of manual and other cutting processes. It makes use of combined operation of a motor connected to a rotating circular disc which is further connected to a shaft which facilitates the reciprocating motion of a perpendicular cutter over the sugarcane, thus facilitating smooth cutting of bud from sugarcane.

Modern Technology for Harvesting: With the time there are moving of farm labour to from agriculture sector leads to the crisis of labour and higher wages resulting as uneconomical in terms of time and cost. Earlier the labour was available enough but with regards of change of time and climate there are difficult to meet the needs only from involvement in agriculture is key point of labour scarcity. There should be efficiently harvesting of crop with reducing of time and wastage; increases the benefits from same field. There is using of technology reducing the dependency on labour and saving of time with timely harvesting. Some of the modern technologies for harvesting of crops like reaper, combine harvester, tea leaf plucking machine, harvester for groundnut and sugarcane etc. are efficiently cut the crops within short duration and economically.

Conclusion: There are many problems are facing by farmers such as: cope with climate change, soil erosion and biodiversity loss, satisfy consumers' changing tastes and expectations, meet rising demand for more food of higher quality etc. while in other land poor economical status with fragmented land restrict the farm mechanization. But with change of time there should be change the practices for mitigating the climate change and migration of people from agriculture. The modern practices of cop production are facilitates to increase farm income with sustainable of resources towards climate change mitigation. There are removal; of unnecessary practices from crop production focusing on biodiversity maintenance and saving of environment from pollution.

Использованная литература:

1. Das, D., Mandal, M. (2016). Advanced Technology of Fertilizer Uses for crop production. Fertilizer Technology, 1: 18-68.
2. El-Sherif, N.A. (2018). Impact of plant tissue culture on agricultural sustainability. In: Negm A, Abu-hashim M (eds) sustainability of agricultural environment in egypt: part ii. The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry, Vol 77. Springer, Cham Frisvold, G., Boor, A. and Reeves, J.M. (2007).
3. Simultaneous diffusion of herbicide tolerant cotton and conservation tillage. In Proceedings of the Beltwide Cotton Conference, Are biotechnology and sustainable agriculture compatible? 15512 January 2007, National Cotton Council of America, New Orleans, LA.
4. Ghasemi, H.D., Navab, F.K., Ghavidel, R.A. (2015). Biotechnology in agriculture and its relationship to the principles of sustainable agriculture. Conference paper Islam, S., Islam, R., Islam, M. (2018).
5. Effects of prilled urea and urea super granule with poultry manure on rice field water property, growth and yield of brridhan 49. International Journal of Plant Biology & Research.
6. Jan, A., Khan, I. and Sohail, A. (2015). Sowing dates and sowing methods influenced on growth yield and yield components of pearl millet under rainfed conditions. Journal of Environment and Earth Science, 5(1): 105-109